

EFFECT OF GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN NIGERIA (1960-2008). A BOUNDS TESTING APPROACH

¹Binuomote S. O. Adeleke O. A. and ²C. O. Omodunbi;

¹Department of Agricultural Economics, Ladoko Akintola University of Technology, P.M.B. 4000, Ogbomoso, Nigeria, ²Department of Agricultural Economics, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of government expenditure on agricultural production in Nigeria between 1960 and 2008. The output of agricultural production proxied as agricultural GDP(LAGDP) was considered as a function of factors such as the amount of the lagged agricultural GDP, exchange rate (LER), government expenditure on agriculture(LEXP), structural adjustment programme (SAP), price of crude oil (LPo) and agricultural land (LD). Estimates, based on the autoregressive distributed lags modeling approach to integration and error correction specification, indicate that the exchange rate (LER), lagged value of agricultural GDP (LAGDP), crude oil price(LPo), structural adjustment programme (SAP), agricultural land (LD) and trend significantly determined agricultural output in Nigeria. The results further show that, the error correction mechanism (ECM) indicated a feedback of about 48.1% of the previous year's disequilibrium from long-run agricultural output.

INTRODUCTION

The role of agriculture in transforming the economic framework of any economy cannot be over emphasized given that it is the source of food for man and animal and provides raw materials for the industrial sector. Thus, it plays a significant role in the reduction of poverty (Nwankwo, 1993). In addition, agriculture provides employment opportunities for the teeming population, and contributes to the growth of the economy (Izuchukwu, 2011). Economic history also provides us with ample evidence that agricultural revolution is a fundamental pre-condition for economic growth, especially in developing countries (Woolf and Jones, 1969; Oluwasanmi, 1966; Eicher and Witt, 1964). Although Nigeria has been an agricultural economy and has targeted the agricultural sector as the principal source of growth and revenue, the role of agriculture in the economy has since independence seem to be experiencing a downward trend due majorly to lack of finance inter alia (Okorie, 1998; Hammond, 2003). Ukeji (2003) submits that in the 1960's, agriculture contributed up to 64% to the total GDP but gradually declined in the 70's to 48% and it continues in 1980 to 20% and 19% in 1985, this was as a result of oil glut of the 1980's. It was also evident that from the increasing food supply shortfalls, rising cost of food processing and delivering, foreign exchange earnings from agricultural exports, agriculture is not given the needed attention to economic development (CBN, 2002).

Government expenditure is perhaps the single most important policy instrument available to governments of most developing countries for promoting growth and equitable distribution. Aside the fact that government expenditure is used to improve technology, human capital and infrastructure development necessary for growth, it also provides the incentives and enabling environment to promote private sector investments to promote further growth. In light of the central role that agriculture plays in the development strategy of most developing countries (Diao et al. 2007), a number of key questions arise: How much public expenditure on the agricultural sector is required to achieve a country's growth and poverty reduction targets? Would allocating 10 percent of national budgetary resources to the agriculture sector, as declared by African heads of state under the Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP) (AU/NEPAD 2003), be sufficient for achieving the millennium development goals (MDGs) in Africa? In the context of agricultural and rural development, how should public expenditure resources be allocated among different types of agricultural public goods and services (e.g. agricultural research, extension, farm input support, etc.), rural infrastructure (e.g. irrigation, roads, markets, etc.), rural social services (e.g. education, health, water, etc.), and across geographic areas for better or improved distributional outcomes and impacts? Answering these policy questions require information on the returns to public spending, particularly agricultural productivity returns to public spending on agriculture and other sectors of the rural economy; a fundamental but scarce knowledge.

The objective of this paper is to investigate the effect of government expenditure on the agricultural productivity in Nigeria bearing in mind that the sector is fundamental to the sustenance of life and the bed rock of economic growth. Among other things, this paper will also examine the trend of agricultural productivity and government expenditure in Nigeria.

The remaining part of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the conceptual framework for this study, the methodology is presented in section 3, the results of the analysis is given in section 4 while the summary, conclusions and policy recommendations to the study is given in section 5.

Conceptual Framework

Link between Government Spending and Agricultural Growth

As stated in Benin *et al* (2009), the issue of how government spending affects agricultural growth is well-established in a growing body of literature. The general notion is that public capital and private capital are complementary factors in the production process, so an increase in the public capital stock raises the productivity of all factors in production (Anderson *et al.* 2006). By raising the productivity of all factors in production, public capital investments crowd-in private capital investments leading to an increase in the private capital stock (David *et al.* 2000; Malla and Gray 2005; Kakwani and Son, 2006), which further contributes to raising productivity. Benin *et al* (2009) stated that crowding-out of private capital investments, with contrasting effects on productivity growth, may also occur. This derives from the relative efficiency of public versus private investments, especially in many developing countries where public sector agencies compete directly with the private sector in the provision of private goods and services. This is because government and private spending is considered a zero-sum game, in the sense that government spending is financed by taxation of private investment. The findings of Ashipala and Haimbodi (2003) on Botswana, South Africa and Namibia, for example, show that private investment is more productive than government investment, suggesting that government investment will result in loss of growth, to the extent that publicly-financed activities were in direct competition with the private sector. It is also possible that government spending may not create any productive capital (Devarajan *et al.* 1996), so the link between public spending and productivity would be weak. Therefore, we can conceptualize the link between the public spending decision and household agricultural production decision as: *direct*, where public spending affects factor productivity; and *indirect*, where public spending affects the use and amount of factors and inputs (or factor accumulation). For example, public spending on research, extension and education leading to improvements in the stock of modern technologies, knowledge and human capital would be expected to raise productivity of all factors of production. Government spending on agricultural input subsidies, on the other hand, would be expected to increase the use and amount of the subsidized inputs. However, an input subsidy can also have substantial indirect price effects on the use and amounts of other inputs. For example, recipients of a subsidy may alter their labor supply or spending and savings choices, which would in turn affect their farm and non-farm production and consumption decisions in a manner that may undermine the expected outcomes of the subsidy program (Van de Walle 2003). By reducing transportation and transactions costs, lowering agricultural input prices and raising farm gate prices, government spending on infrastructure (e.g. roads, input and output markets, marketing information) would also be expected to greater factor accumulation as well as higher value of production.

METHODOLOGY

ARDL Analytical Framework and Model Specification

The study utilizes the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) also known as bound testing procedure developed to examine the co-integration relationship between quantity of agricultural output and its determinants. The choice of this test is based on the following considerations. Firstly, unlike most of the conventional multivariate co integration procedures, which are valid for large sample size, the bound test is suitable for a small sample size study. The sample size used is limited with a total of 45 observations. Secondly, the bounds test does not require the pretesting of the variables included in the model for unit roots unlike other techniques such as the Johansen approach. It is applicable irrespective of whether the regressors in the model are purely I (0), purely I (1) or mutually co integrated. The procedure will however crash in the presence of I (2) series. Thirdly, the bound test is simple as opposed to other multivariate co integration techniques such as Johansen and Juselius (1990), it allows the co integration relationship to be estimated by OLS once the lag order of the model is identified. Following Pesaran *et al.* (2001) as summarized in Choong *et al.* (2005), we apply the

procedure by modeling the long run equation (5) as a general Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model of order p, in

$$z_t = \beta t + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i z_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t, \quad t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, T \quad \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

with c_0 representing a $(k+1)$ -vector of intercepts (drift) and β denoting a $(k+1)$ -vector of trend coefficients. Pesaran *et al.*, (2001) further derived the following vector equilibrium correction model (VECM) corresponding to:

$$\Delta z_t = c_0 + \beta t + \pi z_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \Gamma_i \Delta z_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t, \quad t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, T \quad \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where the $(k+1) \times (k+1)$ matrices $\Pi = I_{k+1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \psi_i$ and $\Gamma_i = -\Pi = \sum_{j=i+1}^p \psi_j, i = 1, 2, \dots, p-1$

contain the long-run multipliers and short-run dynamic coefficients of the VECM. Z_t is the vector of variables y_t and x_t respectively. y_t is an I(1) dependent variable defined as $\ln Y_t$ and

$AGDP_t = (LD, LER, LP_O, LEXP, SAP, FT, T)$ is a vector matrix of ‘forcing’ I(0) and I(1) regressors as already defined with a multivariate identically and independently distributed (*i.i.d*) zero mean error vector $\varepsilon_t = (\varepsilon_{1t}, \varepsilon_{2t})$ and a homoskedastic process. Further assuming that a unique long-run relationship exists among the variables, the conditional VECM of interest can be specified as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta LAGDP = & \delta_0 + LAGDP_{t-1} + \delta_1 LD_{t-1} + \delta_2 LP_{O,t-1} + \delta_3 LEXP_{t-1} + \delta_4 LER_{t-1} + \delta_5 SAP + \delta_6 FT_{t-1} + \delta_7 T + \\ & \sum_{i=0}^p \phi_i \Delta LAGDP_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q w_j \Delta LD_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^q \phi \Delta LEXP_{t-1} + \sum_{m=0}^q y_m \Delta LPO_{t-m} + \sum_{n=1}^q \psi \Delta LER_{t-n} + \sum_{n=1}^q \psi_i \Delta LFT_{t-n} \\ & \dots\dots\dots (3) \end{aligned}$$

where δ are the long run multipliers, c_0 is the drift and ε_t are white noise errors.

There are 3 steps in testing the co integration relationship between the supply of wheat and its explanatory variables. First, we will estimate equation above by ordinary least square (OLS) technique. The presence of co integration can be traced by conducting an F-test for the joint significance of the coefficients of the lagged levels of the variables. That is, the null hypothesis

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 : & \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \delta_3 = \delta_4 = \delta_5 = \delta_6 = \delta_7 = \delta_8 = 0 && \text{against the alternative.} \\ H_a : & \delta_1 \text{ or } \delta_2 \text{ or } \delta_3 \text{ or } \delta_4 \text{ or } \delta_5 \text{ or } \delta_6 \text{ or } \delta_7 \text{ or } \delta_8 \neq 0. \end{aligned}$$

If the computed F- statistic is less than lower bound critical value, then we do not reject the null hypothesis of no co integration. Conversely, if the computed F- statistic is greater than upper bound critical value, then we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there exists steady state equilibrium between the variables under study. However, if the computed F - value falls within lower and upper bound critical values, then the result is inconclusive. The appropriate critical values for the F-tests are obtained. Critical values for the I(0) series are referred to as the upper bound critical values while the critical values for the I(1) series are referred to as lower bound critical values.

Second, assuming a unique long run relationship exists among variables of interest, we specify a conditional ARDL (P, q₁, q₂, q₃, q₄, q₅, q₆, q₇) long run model for $LAGDP_t$ based on equation 2 as

$$\begin{aligned} LAGDP = & C_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i LAGDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_2 LD_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q \alpha_3 LEX_{t-j} + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_4 LPO_{t-1} + \sum_{m=0}^q \alpha_5 LER_{t-m} + \sum_{o=1}^q \alpha_7 LFT_{t-o} + \alpha_7 T + \alpha_8 SAP_{t-1} \\ & \dots (4) \end{aligned}$$

The lags length in the ARDL model is selected based on Schwarz Bayesian criterion (SBC) and Akaike information criterion. For wheat, a maximum of 4 lags will be selected.

In the final text, we obtain the short-run dynamic elasticities by estimating an error correction model associated with the long run estimates. This is specified as follows;-

LAGDP=

$$\alpha + \sum_{l=0}^p \alpha \Delta LAGDP_{t-d} + \sum_{i=1}^q \phi \Delta LD_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^q \omega \ln \Delta LEX_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^q \phi \ln \Delta PO_{t-i} + \sum_{m=1}^q \eta \Delta \ln ER_{t-m} + \sum_{n=1}^q \psi \Delta \ln FT_{t-n} + \lambda ECM_{t-1} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Where $\alpha, \phi, \omega, \phi, \psi, \eta$ are the short-run dynamic elasticities of the model's convergence to long-run equilibrium and λ is the speed of adjustment. Δ represents first difference operated and ECM_{t-1} is the one period lagged error correction term. The coefficient measures the speed of adjustment to obtain equilibrium in the event of shocks to the system. General – to – specific modeling technique of Hendry and Erricson (1991) is followed in selecting the preferred ECM. This procedure first estimate the ECM with different lag lengths for the difference terms and, then, simplify the representation by eliminating the lags with insignificant parameters.

A correctly indicated ECM model has to pass a series of diagnosed tests. These include the Autoregressive LM (Lagrange multiplier) test and/or Durbin-Watson test for serial correlation in the residual, the Autoregressive LM test for normality distribution of the residuals in a regression model, the ARCH and the White test for heteroscedasticity in errors. These tests were conducted to ensure reliability of results.

Model Specification.

The form of model specification for this study is specified as

$$LAGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LD + \beta_2 LP_o + \beta_3 LEXP + \beta_4 LER + \beta_5 SAP + \beta_6 FT + \beta_7 T + e$$

Where:

- LAGDP = Agricultural Gross Domestic Product.
- LD = Land used in Agricultural Production ($\beta_1 > 0$)
- LEXP = Expenditure on Agriculture ($\beta_2 > 0$)
- LER = Real Exchange Rate ($\beta_3 > 0$)
- LPo = Price of Crude oil ($\beta_3 < 0$)
- SAP = Structural Adjustment Programme ($\beta_4 > 0$)
- T = Trend ($\beta_5 > 0$)

Source of Data

The data for this study is a time series data at macro level spanning from 1960 to 2008. Data on Nigeria Agricultural GDP and Government expenditure on agriculture were sourced from various editions of Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin. Data on agricultural land and fertilizer were sourced from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) statistical data base while the data on exchange rate were taken from Penn world data of the University of Pennsylvania

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of ARDL Cointegration test.

Applying the steps, enumerated above, OLS regression was estimated for the first differences part of equation (1) and then test for the joint significance of the parameters of the lagged level variables when added to the first regression. The computed F-statistics was compared with the value from the Pesaran test as reported in table 1, according to the computed F-Statistics; we can reject the null hypothesis of the integration at 1% significance level for output of agricultural production. The computed F-statistics $Fm (LAGDP / LD, LER, LP_o, LEXP, SAP, T) = 4.990$ which is higher than the upper bound critical value of 4.329 at the 5% significance level. This indicates that the alternative hypothesis of the existence of a

unique co integration relationship between agricultural output proxied as Agricultural GDP and specified determinants can be accepted for Nigeria in this case.

In other words, it has been proved that output of agricultural production, Land (LD), Exchange Rate (LER), Price of Crude Oil (LP_0), Government expenditure ($LEXP$) on agriculture, Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) and Trend (T), are bound together in the long run (co integrated) when output of agricultural production is made the dependent variable. The results of the solved static long- run equation for the output of agricultural production in Nigeria as well as its short run equation are given in the table 2 below.

Table 1: ARDL cointegration test for long -run relationship

Critical values	$LAGDP_t = (LD, LER, LP_0, LEXP, SAP,)$ K = 5	4.990
	Lower bound I(0)	Upper bound I(1)
1%	4.011	5.331
5%	3.189	4.329
10%	2.782	3.827

Notes – Case III Critical values are extracted from Pesaran *et al* (2001)

ARDL Static Long-run and Short -run Error Correction Results

The static long- run coefficient and the lagged short run coefficient of land (LD) are -4.950 and -7.931, significant at 10 percent and 5 percent respectively. This is not in line with a priori expectation and is consistent with findings of Olagaju and Falola (1996). The negative sign supports the hypothesis that environmental pollution and alarming population growth rate have greatly reduced land meant for agriculture. The Government should strengthen its efforts on not only providing land for agriculture but providing cultivatable land. In the short –run however, coefficient of land is 5.653 and significant at 10 percent. This indicates that 1 unit increase in land would increase agricultural output by 5.653 units.

The coefficient of Exchange Rate (LER) in the long- run is 0.043 but it is not significant statistically, which supports the current trend of event in the country that exchange rate devaluation is not having its desired effect in the long-run. In the short-run however, Exchange rate (lagged one year) has a coefficient of -0.094 and it is significant at 5% level. The short-run results suggests that as the nation’s currency gets devalued, importation will be discouraged and there will be a stimulation of more domestic agricultural production to meet the needs of the nation and provide surplus for export.

The coefficient for price of crude oil (LP_0) is negative as expected and highly significant at 1 percent. This implies that a unit increase in the price of crude oil would lead to a decrease in agricultural output by 0.178 units. This is true for Nigeria because petroleum products remain the main source of government earnings and agriculture is taken as a backup plan. Agriculture was the mainstay of the Nigerian economy until the discovery of crude oil and the agricultural sector began to be neglected 1970’s. Today, petroleum is the main source of foreign exchange to the Nigerian economy. Increase in the international price of crude oil will drive the government to increase the output to the detriment of the industrial and agricultural sector.

The coefficient for Government expenditure ($LEXP$) is 0.258 in the long – run but it is not significant statistically. In the short-run, the coefficient is 0.041 and it is also insignificant statistically. Although the coefficient is positive both in the long -run and short run as one will expect one will expect, it does not have the expected significant effect on agricultural output in Nigeria. This finding is however is backed up by the findings of Moguees *et al* (2008), which reveal that Nigeria falls behind in capital funding not because money is not allocated to the sector, but budget execution is poor due to high rate of corruption in Nigeria. However adequate measures have to been taken to reduce corruption in Nigeria.

Trend refers to all factors inherent in time such as expenditure on agriculture, application of modern techniques, and use of improved seeds for cultivation, agricultural extension services. The coefficient for

Trend is 0.051 and highly significant at 1 percent. This implies that an improvement in agriculture through activities such as application of modern techniques and adequate extension services is essential to increase agricultural output.

The coefficient of error correction term (ECM) carries the expected negative sign and it is significant at 1%. The significance of the ECM supports co-integration and suggests the existence of long – run steady state equilibrium between wheat import and other determining factors in the specified model. The coefficient of - 0.481 indicates that the deviation of agricultural production from the long-run equilibrium level is corrected by about 48.1% in the current period.

Diagnostic Test Discussions.

The Autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (ARCH) test for testing heteroscedasticity in the error process in the model has an F-statistic of 1.762 which statistically insignificant. This suggests that there is no heteroscedasticity in the model. The Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test for higher order – serial correlation with an F-statistic of 0.130 which is also statistically insignificant could not reject the null of absence of serial correlation in the residuals.

The Jacque – Bera χ^2 – statistic of 0.067 for the normality in the distribution in the error process shows that the error process is normally distributed. From the battery of diagnostic tests presented above, this study concludes that the model is well estimated and that the observed data fits the model specification adequately, thus the residuals are expected to be distributed as white noise and the coefficient valid for policy discussions.

Table 2: Short- run Error Correction Modeling of the Effect of Government Expenditure on Agricultural productions in Nigeria

ARDL (1, 0, 0, 0, 1) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion

Dependent variable is LM 49 observations were used for estimation (1960 – 2008)

Static Long – run equation		Parsimonious Short – run equation	
Constant	56.795 (1.872)*	Constant	-10.932 (-3.535)***
<i>LD</i>	-4.950 (-1.841)*	Δ LAGDP	0.259 (1.736)*
<i>LEXP</i>	0.258 (1.589)	Δ LD	5.563 (1.715)*
<i>LER</i>	0.043 (1.251)	Δ LD (-1)	-7.931 (-2.856)**
<i>SAP</i>	-2.661 (-1.893)*	Δ LEXP	0.041 (0.872)
<i>LP_o</i>	-0.178 (-3.611)***	Δ LER	0.708 (2.099)**
<i>Trend</i>	0.051 (5.134)***	Δ SAP	-0.801 (-1.380)
		Δ LP _o	-0.129 (-2.717)**
		<i>ECM</i> (-1)	-0.481 (-4.244)***
		R ²	= 0.351
		AR LM F	= 1.131 (0.720)
		ARCH F	= 1.762 (0.191)
		Normality χ^2	= 0.067 (0.967)

Source: Data analysis, 2010. *** means significant at 1%, ** means significant at 5%, * means significant at 10%,

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATION.

The results of this study show that there government funding though have positive effect on agricultural production in Nigeria, the effect is not significant. While it has been identified that funding is not the problem of agricultural production in Nigeria, corruption is major problem militating against agricultural productivity in Nigeria. Government should therefore ensure that funds meant for implementing various agricultural policies in Nigeria are not only released, efforts should made to monitor the disbursement and allocation of such funds so that it gets to the desired ends.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, E., de Renzio, P. and Levy, S. (2006). The role of public investment in poverty reduction: theories, evidence and methods. Working Paper 23, Overseas Development Institute, London, UK.
- Ashipala J and N Haimbodi. (2003) The Impact of Public Investment on Economic Growth in Namibia. Working Paper # 88. The Namibian Economic Policy Research Unit.
- AU/NEPAD (2003). *Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme*. NEPAD, Midrand, South Africa.
- Benin S., Mogues T, Cudjoe G, and Randriamamonjy J (2009) Public Expenditures and Agricultural Productivity Growth in Ghana. Contributed Paper, IAAE, Beijing 2009
- Choong C. K., Y. Zulkoranic and K. S. Venus (2005). Export-led growth hypothesis in Malaysia: An investigation using bound test. *Sunway Acad. J.*, 2: 13-22.
- David, P.A., Hall, B.H. and Toole, A.A. (2000). Is public R&D a complement or substitute for private R&D? A review of the econometric evidence *Research Policy* 29(4-5):497-529.
- Devarajan S, Swaroop V, Zou H, (1996). The Composition of Public Expenditure and Economic Growth. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 37: 313-344.
- Diao, X., Hazell, P., Resnick, D. and Thurlow, J. (2007). The role of agriculture in development: implications for sub-Saharan Africa. Research Report 153, International Food Policy Research Institute, Washington, D.C., USA.
- Eicher, C. and Witt, L. (eds.) (1964) *Agriculture in Economic Development New York*: McGraw Hill, London.
- Hammond, R. (2003). The Impact of IMF Structural Adjustment Policies on Tanzanian Agriculture. <http://www.developmentgap.org/imftanzania.html>
- Hendry K. And V. Erricson (1991). Time Series Analysis and Economic Modelling. Zed Press, London, 17: 255- 299.
- Johansen, S. and K. Juselius, (1990). Maximum likelihood of estimation and interference on cointegration with application to the demand for money. *Oxford Bull. Econ. Stat.*, 52: 169- 210.
- Jones, E. I. and Woolf, S. S. (eds) (1969), *Agrarian change and Economic Development: The Historical problem* London: Methuen
- Kakwani, N. and Son, H.H. (2006). How costly is it to achieve the millennium development goal of halving poverty between 1990 and 2015? International Poverty Center Working Paper 19, UNDP.
- Malla, S. and Gray, R (2005) The crowding effects of basic and applied research: a theoretical and empirical analysis of an agricultural biotech industry. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 87(2):423-438
- Mouges A. S., E. S. Folorunsho, D. W. Oguntana, T. E. Nnamani (2008). The Nigerian Economic Development and Agriculture. Ibadan University Press. University of Ibadan, Ibadan Nigeria.

Nwankwo, G. O. (1983). "Agricultural Finance Policy and Strategy in the 1980" In: Ojo, M. O., Edodu, C. C. and Akinbade, J. A. (eds) Nigeria: Problems and Prospects. Published by the Central Bank of Nigeria, Lagos.

Olagbaju J., and T. Falola (1996) Post independence Economic Changes and Development in West Africa. In Oguremi G. O., Faluyi E. K. (eds) An Economic History of West Africa Since 1750. Ibadan: Rex Charles.

Oluwasanmi, H. A. (1966), *Agriculture and Nigeria's Economic Development Ibadan*: Ibadan University Press

Pesaran M. H., Shin and R. J. Smith (2001). Bound Testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*. 16: 289-326.

Izuchukwu O. (2011) Analysis of the Contribution of Agricultural Sector on the Nigerian Economic Development. *World Review of Business Research Vol. 1. No. 1. March 2011. Pp. 191 – 200*

Ukeje, R. O. (2003) *Macroeconomics: An Introduction*, Port Harcourt Davidson Publication

van de Walle, D. (2003). Behavioral incidence analysis of public spending and social programs. In Bourguignon, F. and da Silva, L.A.P. (Eds.). *The impact of economic policies on poverty and income distribution: evaluation techniques and tools*. Washington, DC: World Bank.

Received for Publication: 25/05/12

Accepted for Publication: 15/07/12

Corresponding author

Binuomote S. O.

Department of Agricultural Economics, Ladoko Akintola University of Technology, P.M.B. 4000,

Ogbomoso, Nigeria

Email:lanresamuel@hotmail.com